

**AI-POWERED SYSTEM FOR DETECTING OBSTRUCTIONS BLOCKING
STAIRWELLS IN HIGH-RISE BUILDINGS****Shueh-Cheng Hu**Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science & Communication Engineering,
Providence University,
Taiwan, ROC**ABSTRACT**

This article reports a work aiming to identify obstructions in high-rise buildings' stairwells. Objects left in the stairwells of tall buildings pose a serious safety risk, especially in the event of fire or evacuation. However, to conduct manual inspections of stairwell obstructions is extremely time-consuming and inefficient, especially in tall buildings. Artificial intelligence techniques including a neural network computer vision model: YOLOv8, were applied in the prototype of a stairwells obstructions detection system. Dual models of objects were trained and applied for achieving better flexibility in this kind of solutions. Before widely adopting this kind of system, further works including models that can detect a wider variety of object categories and efficient ways of capturing video sources are required.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, Dual Models, Property Management, High-rise Building

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring unobstructed stairwells in high-rise buildings is critical for maintaining safe and efficient emergency evacuation routes. In emergency scenarios such as fires or natural disasters, stairwells serve as critical evacuation routes. Any obstruction within these pathways can severely impede safe passage, leading to increased risk of injury, fatality, and delayed emergency response. Manual methods are inherently limited by its labor-intensive characteristic, and thus could be conducted only in an infrequent and non-real-time way. In consequence, manually inspecting these areas is prone to oversight, especially in large or densely populated high-rise buildings. Low frequency of checking prevents the provision of in-time alerts, which are critical in dynamic environments where obstructions can appear suddenly and pose immediate risks to people's safety or life.

To address this challenge, we proposed an intelligent system that leverages artificial intelligence and advanced computer vision techniques to automatically detect and identify obstructions in stairwells. This kind of systems automatically detect unsafe conditions and alert appropriate personnel before an accident occurs, can significantly enhance the safety of buildings and people within them. This approach represents a fundamental shift from reactive to proactive property management scheme.

RELEVANT STUDIES

Ensuring clear egress pathways in high-rise buildings is critical, governed by stringent regulations. For instance, OSHA regulations (29 CFR 1910.36) specify that exit routes must be free of obstructions, maintaining a minimum width of 28 inches (71.1 cm) at all points, with no projections reducing this clearance [1]. These codes also emphasize the importance of clear marking of obstacles to prevent hazards.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have significantly enhanced safety and surveillance functionality in public and private spaces. AI-enabled smart video solutions (SVS) integrate with existing camera networks to provide real-time alerts and anomaly detection, transforming passive surveillance into proactive safety management [2]. In safety-critical contexts, such as autonomous systems, ML perception functions are increasingly used, necessitating robust safety monitoring mechanisms due to challenges like the "black-box nature" of models and potential over-confidence in predictions [3].

Within computer vision domain, object detection is a foundational task for identifying and localizing objects in images and videos [4]. Deep learning-based methods have advanced significantly, though challenges persist with occlusions, varying object scales, and improving real-time processing capabilities [4-5]. YOLOv8, a computer vision model with prominent object detection algorithms, has demonstrated its high accuracy (92.6%) and mean average precision (mAP@0.5) of 95% for obstacle detection in structured indoor environments, often leveraging RGB-D sensors for depth information [6]. While YOLO has been successfully applied to staircase detection for robotic navigation, showing robustness to occlusions by artificial and natural objects [7], and some frameworks use it for road obstacle detection with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [8], specific applications for building interior obstruction detection for human safety compliance are less explored. Furthermore, vision-language models (VLMs) are emerging for 3D object detection and indoor scene understanding, capable of generating spatial hierarchical scene graphs and providing distance information [9-10]. Techniques like implicit object memory also enhance embodied object detection by aggregating features across temporal horizons, improving robustness to sensor noise and domain shift in indoor scenes [11]. Automated systems have also utilized laser scanners and infrared sensors for obstacle sensing on staircases, primarily for robot navigation and alignment [12].

METHODOLOGY

This work proposed a system aiming to identify obstructions in high-rise buildings' stairwells, then record all obstructions that lead to potential risks. The architecture of the prototyped system is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1 System Architecture

The process of building up the system include the following 4 major stages of works:

1. Data collection: acquiring images of stairwells with obstructions, and images of stairwell floor numbers marked on the wall. For better generalization of AI models, this dataset of images must be captured from various high-rise building stairwells, encompassing a wide range of environmental factors. These factors reflect variations in lighting (e.g., bright daylight, low light, emergency lighting) and angles (viewpoints). In the prototyped system, there are about 1,000 images collected for identifying boxes and stairwell floor numbers, respectively.
2. Image annotation: The Roboflow, an online platform designed to streamline computer vision projects by providing tools for dataset management, model training, and deployment [13], was used to label various types of potential obstructions in collected images, such as boxes, furniture, and cleaning equipment in non-compliant areas. During this stage, 3 augmentation functions of the Roboflow including geometric transformations, color adjustments, and noise injection, were used to improve computer vision model's generalization.

3. Model training: The model training task was performed within the Google Colab environment. The YOLOv8 was used as the basis to train two models; one model for detecting the category of obstructions, and another model for identifying where (which floor) an obstruction was found. The rationale of using dual models is that the system can have better flexibility since two models could be trained and deployed separately. The key parameters set for training the models include epochs: 800, batch size: 32. The values of 2 loss functions (box_loss & cls_loss) for the model dealing with obstruction objects were 0.46 and 0.39, respectively, and were 0.38 and 0.41 for the model recognizing floor numbers.
4. System integration: two deployed AI models were integrated with a Python-based backend framework: Flask and a data storage mechanism: Firebase in the prototype. Besides, some front-end Web pages were developed and deployed to serve users of the proposed system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visual examples from the experimental trials as shown in figure 2 demonstrate the two AI models' capability to successfully detect and classify category of stairwell obstructions, as well as the floor numbers. Annotated video frames clearly show bounding boxes around objects such as boxes in non-compliant areas. The system exhibited robust performance in typical indoor lighting conditions and for objects of varying scales.

Figure 2 Experimental Results

Quantitative performance metrics of the 2 models are summarized in table 1. The contrast between the precision and recall rates of the obstruction detection model implied that in safety-critical applications such as the prototyped system, the cost of a false negative (a missed obstruction) should be higher than the cost of a false positive. Therefore, one key task is to tune the object detection model to maximize its recall rate, which minimizes the risk of an undetected hazard. However, this approach inherently involves a compromise on precision, as a more sensitive model will inevitably generate more alerts, but some of which may be unwarranted.

Metric	Model for Obstructions	Model for floor numbers
mAP@.50	0.852	0.786
mAP@.50:.95	0.696	0.603

Precision	0.897	0.852
Recall	0.751	0.706
F1-score	0.817	0.772

Table 1. Model Performance Metrics

During the initial stage of model training, we tried to put images of boxes and floor number marks together, and encountered the catastrophic forgetting phenomenon [14-15], which states that when a neural network forgets previously learned information of boxes upon learning new information of floor number marks. This is a common challenge in machine learning tasks, especially in models that are fine-tuned on new datasets. When we tried to fine-tune a YOLOv8 model with a new dataset containing floor number marks, the model's weights are updated to minimize the loss for this new dataset. As a result, the weights that were important for recognizing boxes might be altered or overwritten, leading to a loss of the model's ability to recognize those obstruction objects. In consequence, we tried to use dual models for recognizing obstruction objects and floor number marks, respectively. The new approach makes 2 models could be trained simultaneously without mutual interference.

A key factor will significantly influence the usability of this kind of system is how easy the system can acquire video sources showing the context of interest. The cameras fixed-mounted on the walls can capture images of context in limited angles, thus might leave blind spots. An alternative way to acquire images of context within stairwells is using indoor drones, which can dynamically capture images from various angles, and can interact with the detection system in real-time, and thus improve the responsiveness of the detection system.

CONCLUSIONS

This research presents a significant advancement in building safety, demonstrating the effectiveness of an AI-powered computer vision system for stairwell obstruction detection in high-rise buildings. The system leverages state-of-the-art object detection techniques, enhanced with temporal and spatial reasoning capabilities, to accurately identify and record obstructions that violate critical safety regulations. By providing highly available and automated inspection mechanism, this work transforms traditional, reactive safety checking scheme into a proactive, data-driven approach, significantly enhancing emergency preparedness and ensuring compliance with building and fire safety standards.

Three major promising works exist for future research and development; the first one is expanding generalization that needs more diverse datasets, encompassing a wider range of obstruction types, extreme lighting conditions, and varied camera viewpoints. This will enhance the system's robustness and generalization capabilities, allowing it to perform reliably in a broader spectrum of real-world scenarios. The second work is developing seamless integration with existing property management system, fire alarm systems, and broader emergency response platforms. This integration would enable automated alerts, real-time data sharing, and coordinated responses, potentially including automated triggering of audio warnings or visual cues within stairwells. The third future work is the integration of the obstruction detection system and indoor drones which can capture footage from various perspectives in real-time and could be programmed for much more dynamic behavior, such as re-scanning suspicious spots immediately to verify the actual presence of obstructions.

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